

PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF FATHER IMAGE FORMATION IN THE FAMILY

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6968962>

Ismatova Dilafruz Toymurodovna
Uzbekistan. Bukhara State University

Annotation: *In this article, various psychological approaches to the image of the father in the family and the scientific theoretical basis of the image of the father in the image of children are presented.*

Key words: *Image, imagination, perception, communication, cultural stereotypes, appearance, responsibility, respect, education, intelligence, care, virtue, personality.*

Аннотация: *В данной статье представлены различные психологические подходы к образу отца в семье и научно-теоретические основы образа отца в образе детей.*

Ключевые слова: *Образ, воображение, восприятие, общение, культурные стереотипы, внешний вид, ответственность, уважение, воспитание, интеллигентность, забота, добродетель, личность.*

Relevance of the topic.

Understanding the role of the father in the mental development of each person largely depends on socio-cultural processes. The question of the father's role in the family is one of the main problems of today. The father is the head of the house as a role model for the children.

The concept of "father image" itself is understood by authors in different ways. A.V. Litvinova and N.G. Bolshakova¹ gives the following definition: "The child's perception of the differences in the psychological qualities of the father and mother, which determine the development of the future personality." A.A. Solovieva² suggests images of real and ideal parenting as well as self-images as parents. Kalina and Kholmogorova consider the image of the father as an

¹ Литвинова А.В., Большакова Н.Г. Зависимость ориентировки супругов в конфликте от образов родителей, сформированных в детстве // Материалы Второй Всероссийской научной конференции «Психологические проблемы современной российской семьи»: в 3ч. Ч.2 / под общ. Ред. Д-ра психол. Наук

² Соловьева А.А. Роль образа родителя в социализации детей, воспитывающихся вне семьи // Материалы Второй Всероссийской научной конференции «Психологические проблемы современной российской семьи»: в 3ч. Ч.3 / под общ. Ред. Д-ра психол. Наук В. К. Шабельникова и канд. Психол. Наук А.Г. Лидерса. М., 2005. С. 318-320

important structure that is formed from birth under the influence of internal (forecasts, fantasies) and external (communication with important relatives, cultural stereotypes and direct interaction with the father) defined as it also reflects the physical, intellectual, and emotional components of the father figure. There is a complex relationship between these factors, for example, the child feels the mother's relationship with the father, but can form it based on his own images and imagination.

If we follow the assumption about the child's innate knowledge about the father, then this is a unique process, on the basis of which the child builds the image of the parent. In addition, the child is in direct contact with his father, connecting them with his images and imagination.

In the period of early development, according to D. Uzel, the connection between the partial objects of the father and the mother is very important. If there is precedence over the parent objects, they will "absorb anything and everything". Paternity objects allow this system to be balanced, and if this does not happen, "illusions of discussing partial paternity objects" arise.

Some four- or five-year-old children, as a rule, have negative feelings towards their father, they perceive him as a rival. Children's fantasies of abandonment are designed to distance themselves from their parents and are built around the idea that the child is adopted and that his parents are not real. And in adolescence, children's fantasies are connected with reality, as a result of which the images of parents are not idealized and come closer to reality. Now the image of the parents is criticized, causing disappointment. There is a conflict between the idealized image of the parent and the still lower image of the self.

In many countries, research on the role of the father figure in the family is not perfect. For example: A Japanese woman returned to her parents' home after becoming pregnant and lived there until the child was born. After giving birth, the woman returned to her husband, but she slept in the same bed with the child, not with her husband, until she was at least three years old. A man in such a family rarely communicates with his wife and child and stays at work for a long time. The situation has developed in the same way in Korea and China. Its predominance began to decline in the second half of the 19th century, and in the second half of the 20th century, they gained equal rights with women and began to spend more time with children, which is especially noticeable in the communication of men with their daughters.

In Eastern countries, until recently, the father was the authority and had a dominant position in the traditional family system. The father is the breadwinner

of the family, and in most cases, he repeats the role of manager rather than as an educator.

The emergence of family psychotherapy made it possible to make the approach to the study of the father's role in the context of the family system more holistic. Now the father is considered not only as a breadwinner, but the role of a companion, protector, spouse in the family is included in the perspective of researchers (Lamb M., Tamis-Lemonda C., 2004).

R.V. Ovcharova's study of ideas about ideal fatherhood made it possible to distinguish nine types of ideas among 19-25-year-olds:

"responsible father" - according to the testers, the main characteristic of a father is responsibility. Responsibility is a conscious need for them to fulfill their obligations, equivalent to a sense of duty, only a mature person can take responsibility;

"teaching father" - the husband must be ready to be a father and be able to teach the child. It refers to the father's ability to take on the responsibility of raising a well-rounded person;

"cooperative father" - according to young people, a husband should be responsible and ready to parent, teach and love. He is a businessman and selfless. A father should pay attention to his children, respect them, cooperate with them and, at the same time, always be in a good mood;

"dominant father" - a strong person who is proud of his child; sometimes a father is not afraid to yell at his child and apologize if he is wrong;

"reverential father" - one who respects children, should be proud and interested in them; "altruistic father" - loving, forgiving, not afraid to ask for forgiveness, responsible and nurturing;

"believing father" - a believer, who loves and respects his children, who is ready for fatherhood, who is not afraid to admit his fault and who teaches; "judging father" - strong, strict, intelligent, business man. A father should be fair and forgiving, respectful of his children, sometimes yelling, but not afraid to ask for forgiveness. He often praises his child, takes care of him, is always ready to listen to him;

"nurturing father" - strong, smart, business-like and responsible, believes in his children, always understands and respects them. Always happy, cheerful, kind, pleased with her children. ³A father should be nurturing, experienced, and at the same time, he may not know something. In the family, the father's task is to raise

³ Parenthood as a psychological phenomenon R. V. Ovcharova ISBN: 5-89502-771-7 Year of publication: 2006

children correctly and to overcome a number of problems in order to take their place in society. Children form a number of characteristics from their fathers, such as compassion, endurance, courage and correct speech. Fathers are ideal for children, but they are not ideal for society.

For example, S.T. Posokhova and S.V.Lippo's research shows that men and women have similar ideas about the ideal father, and that they depend on stereotypes in society at this stage of historical development, and not on the real experience of interaction with the father. Throughout the history of mankind, the role of the father in the education of children has always changed. O.G. Kalina and A.B. In their work, the Kholmogorovas analyzed ideas about the role of the father on the example of different cultures.

Yu.E. Aleshina and A.S. According to Volovich, in Russia there are very limited masculinity qualities to show a child's freedom, because adults (mostly women) are ambivalent about such events. This can be seen in the example of the manifestation of resentment: in such a situation, masculine ways of responding are not offered at all or are rejected by parents.

Posokhova and Lippo hypothesize that the father still appears as a dominant figure in the Russian family tradition.

According to the research, the hierarchy of features representing the image of the father is almost independent of the age and gender of the respondents and is expressed in recognition of the authoritarianism and egoism of fathers, and almost no perception of the father's subordinate position is expressed.

Instead of a conclusion, it should be emphasized that the image of the father is formed under the influence of various factors and affects the child's personality, emotional well-being, self-esteem, and mental behavior of the child and adolescent. is an important structure of development. Most of the teenagers especially appreciate the live communication with their father and want to spend more time with him. The image of the father in teenagers is characterized by a complex structure and ambiguous content. The most important personal characteristics of a father for teenagers are kindness, sense of humor, strength, intelligence, care and the ability to help.

REFERENCES:

1. Litvinova A.V., Bolshakova N.G. The dependence of the orientation of spouses in conflict on the images of parents formed in childhood // Materials of

the Second All-Russian Scientific Conference "Psychological problems of the modern Russian family": in 3 hours. Part 2 / under general. Ed. Dr. psikhol. Science

2. Solovieva A.A. The role of the image of the parent in the socialization of children raised outside the family // Materials of the Second All-Russian Scientific Conference "Psychological problems of the modern Russian family": in 3 hours. Part 3 / under the total. Ed. Dr. psikhol. Sciences V. K. Shabelnikova and Cand. Psych. Nauk A.G. Leaders. M., 2005. S. 318-320

3. Parenthood as a psychological phenomenon R. V. Ovcharova ISBN: 5-89502-771-7 Year of publication: 2006

4. To'ymurodovna, I. D. (2021). SPECIFIC PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF PARENTAL COOPERATION IN CHILD REARING. *ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions*, 2(04), 75-80.

5. Tuymuratovna, I. D. (2022). Socio-psychological features of correction of adolescents' emotional stress in the family. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 12(4), 116-118.

6. Исмадова, Д. Т. (2022). Социально-психологические особенности отношений в молодой семье. *Science and Education*, 3(2), 1147-1154.

7. Risnawati, W. I., Astuti, M., Shaxlo, T., Dilafruz, I., & Dilnoza, K. Effect of Work Conflict, Work Stress and Satisfaction working on Employee Erformance at PT. Federal International Financegroup (FIF-Group) Sidoarjo. *International Journal on Economics, Finance and Sustainable Development*, 4(4), 69-80.

8. Izatovna, T. S., & Murtazoyevna, Q. D. (2022). МАКТАБ YOSHIDAGI EGIZAKLARNING O'QISHDAGI MUAMMOLARNI KORREKTSIYALASH YO'LLARI. *TA'LIM VA RIVOJLANISH TAHLILI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 2(3), 220-223.

9. Исмадова, Д. Т. (2022). Социально-психологические особенности коррекции эмоциональных напряжений подростков в семье. *Science and Education*, 3(5), 1317-1325.

10. Исмадова, Д. Т. (2016). РОЛЬ СЕМЬИ В ОБЩЕСТВЕ. *NovInfo. Ru*, 3(57), 556-560.